

Forgive us, we are not too late!: The AI Sector in Africa.

Allan Ochola

Abstract

With a global vision, Africa is expanding and opening up on all fronts. This expansion has ostensibly heralded a confluence of interests between Africa and other world powers and added new elements to the concept of AI governance. However, Africa's digital existence is simultaneously being reshaped by colonial legacies: the mental reality of being African has consequently been sent into a state of cognitive dissonance. This means that on collective and individual levels, denizens of this continent are faced with having to reconcile new realities and actions with hugely discrepant self-understandings. This article will not present a state-by-state overview of digital colonialism or AI readiness: Nor will it seek to paint the continent with one brush by prescribing uncalibrated recommendations for such a diverse continent. Instead, it will take a regional approach to analyzing its institutions and data-driven technological instruments. This is a useful vantage point because it addresses the demand for continental consensus while acknowledging that regional and national implementation will differ. Visions of enhancing science, technology and innovation (STI) driven through the strategy for (STI) for Africa needs to be pulled forward with an eye to decolonial and post-pandemic realities.

Keywords: Innovation, Colonialism, Technology, Open Science.

Introduction

In 2017, the late high profile physicist Stephen Hawking warned that the proliferation of AI could be the “worst event in the history of our civilization” unless the society finds a way to control its development. At the recently released findings from Oxford insights on Government AI Readiness Index 2020, a report that ranks governments around the world according to their readiness to implement AI in the delivery of public services to their citizens, African countries ranked poorly with Mauritius, the highest ranked, in 45th position and 14 African countries occupying the bottom 20 positions of the 172 countries included in the study (Insights, 2020). The Global Innovation Index 2020, arguably the most authoritative index, identified ten African states as ‘Innovation Achievers’ namely Kenya, Malawi, Rwanda, Mozambique, Madagascar, South Africa, Tunisia, Tanzania, Morocco and Niger, but Africa collectively still ranks as the lowest region on overall innovation scores (Cornell University, INSEAD, and WIPO, 2020). This article will not

present a state-by-state overview of AI or innovation readiness: Nor will it seek to paint the continent with one brush by prescribing uncalibrated recommendations for such a diverse continent. Instead, it will focus on the regional approach, institutions and instruments. This is a useful vantage point because it addresses continental consensus but understands that regional and national implementation will differ (Ncube, 2021).

While few African countries are in a position to develop AI strategies, the African Union AI Working Group met for the first time in 2019 aiming to develop a regional approach to AI and information exchange expertise between countries (Data guidance, 2019). This followed commitments made during the Internet Governance Forum presided over by the African Union in November 2018 under the theme of “Development of the Digital Economy and Emerging Technologies in Africa” which focused on several key areas such as democratization of access to internet and capacity building at all levels to ensure that African policymakers, users and innovators are ready for the IoT and Big Data usage for policy makers, users and innovators (Mueller, 2018). As more governments become AI ready, there is growing awareness of the need to develop and use these technologies in a responsible manner. At its 31st extraordinary session held virtually in February 2021, with the aim of undertaking a study on the relationship of human rights and artificial intelligence (AI), robotics and other new and emerging technologies in Africa, The African Commission on Human and Peoples' Rights recognized that these technologies present both opportunities and perils for the promotion and protection of human and people's rights in Africa (ACHPR, 2021).

COVID-19 has reminded us that plagues shake things up, and can lead to an accelerated integration of digital technologies with traditional industries and the real economy. Much as they infect the body, pandemics infect the body politic. They move through our social systems, find vulnerabilities to exploit. In the process, they lay bare those vulnerabilities to scrutiny and afford opportunities for self-reflection. Several projects to develop contact tracing apps commenced soon after the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic (Pearce, 2020). The AU High Level Panel on Emerging Technologies (APET) authored a White Paper in August 2020 that called for open approaches to sourcing medicines and technologies required to meet the COVID-19 pandemic (AUDA-NEPAD, 2020). It cited examples of ongoing work such as: A team at the University of Cape Town's development of Covi-ID32; a contact tracing opensource platform for African contexts which have limited smartphone penetration (Ibid; Strategic Health Innovation Partnerships & the Technology Innovation Agency, 2020). Several other projects have been mounted on the African continent and some were showcased at ECA's Innovation & Investment Forum's Innovation Challenge in June 2020, which called for entries in (ECA, 2020b): Affordable rapid testing; enhanced medical devices and personal protection gear

design and fabrication; alternative tools for efficient and effective contact tracing and isolation; development and production of potential drugs and vaccines in Africa. 168 entries were received, from which 29 were shortlisted to showcase their work at the Forum (ECA, 2020a), and seven winners were selected (ECA, 2020c).

With a global vision Africa is expanding and opening up on all fronts. From maritime to aerospace, foreign trade to the future of work. Amid mounting global challenges policymakers and technologists need to work together to enhance AI governance. Likewise, institutions such as the International Telecommunications Union (ITU) and United Nations Education Science and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) need to advance reform of the technology standards and governance system. Developing countries and Africa in particular, are showing a strong desire to engage in global AI governance. They are also gaining a stronger ability to do so. Africa has hosted major events such as the Internet Governance Forum (*Chair's Summary*, n.d.), and Morocco jointly hosted the 2018 'Forum on Artificial Intelligence in Africa' with UNESCO (UNESCO, 2018). These have demonstrated the confluence of interests between Africa and other world powers and added new elements to the concept of AI governance. Africa-tech ecosystems have always had ebbs and flows, at times tinged with doses of poor policies, and lack of infrastructure and the availability of human capital, but the stakes are much higher today for policymakers, academics and business community because the problems confronting us are much greater. However, these should not be an excuse for lagging behind in the development of the global AI innovation of policy environments but rather an incentive for cooperation.

The digital economy is where Africa's development opportunity lies coupled with a strong belief in Kasparov's law: weak human+ machine+ strong process beats a strong computer alone or a strong human alone; and, more remarkably is superior to a strong human+ machine+ inferior process (Cabitza et al., 2021). As Africa enters a new phase of automation, a people-oriented approach needs to be at the front and center in the digital evolution. This will require a clear plan to improve our competitiveness and encourage productive collaborations. Such collaborations should involve working with various sectors outside the government to strengthen AI research, knowledge, skills and policies. Alongside the continental and global development agendas- Agenda 2063 and SDGs, the civil society, academia, intergovernmental organizations and the private sector, which continue to grow apace, have their own development agenda informed by Africa's unique circumstances, which has spurred scholarship on various aspects of AI. This has been witnessed throughout the history of human civilization where these sectors have led successive revolutions on agriculture, industry and more recently information. The information age has generated the global village concept along with global interconnection, great mobility of people, and interdependence of

countries in economy and information. It is obvious the trend of globalization is not subject to the will of humans and seems irreversible.

Decolonizing Technology in Africa

At this pivotal moment of Africa's history it is important to acknowledge that colonial legacies are very much alive and well across the African continent. While traditional colonialism has been often spearheaded by political and government forces, digital colonialism is driven by corporate tech agendas. Legacies of coloniality perpetuate the establishment of patterns of power between colonizer and colonized—and the contemporary remnants of these relationships. They influence how that power shapes our understanding of culture, labor, intersubjectivity and knowledge production(Quijano, 2000). The frame colonialism used here not as a mere metaphor, nor as an echo or simple continuation of historic forms of territorial colonialism, but to refer to a new form of colonialism distinctive of the 21st century: Digital colonialism (Alaimo, Christina; Jannis, 2017). Digital colonialism manifests in the form of socio-cultural imaginations, knowledge systems and ways of developing and using technology which are based on systems, institutions, and values which persist from the past and remain unquestioned in the present. As such, invasion of emerging technologies like AI in Africa echoes colonial era exploitation, and using the lens of decolonial critical theories we can have useful tools with which to qualify the nature of power imbalances or inequitable impacts that arise from advanced technologies like AI(Mohamed et al., 2020). Digital colonialism combines the predatory extractive practices of historical colonialism with the abstract quantification methods of computing. Just as historical colonialism over the long run provided the essential preconditions for the emergence of industrial capitalism, so over time, can we expect that digital capitalism will provide the preconditions for a new age of capitalism that as yet we can barely imagine, but for which the appropriation of human life through data will be central. The priority at the moment is not to speculate about that eventual stage of capitalism but to resist the digital colonialism that is underway.

As we observe how Africa's digital existence is being reshaped by these colonial legacies, the mental reality of being African has been sent into a state of cognitive dissonance. This means that on collective and individual levels, denizens of this continent are faced with having to reconcile new realities and actions with hugely discrepant self-understandings academics, members of civil society and journalists within the continent and beyond have accurately described how technology that are developed from Western perspectives are unfit for African problems(Birhane, 2020) .This includes the strategies that they put into place to undo the colonial mechanisms of power, economics, language, culture and thinking that shape contemporary life: To confront this, there is a need to interrogate the provenance

and legitimacy of dominant forms of knowledge, values, norms and assumptions. We must confront and resolve the contradictions between today's realities and our long held, sometimes centuries-old cultural beliefs. In practical terms, present strategizing for Africa's digital future has been shaped as much by the continent's descent into dependence on Western software and infrastructure which has led to a sharp increase in digital inequalities informed by financial and political instability, lack of digital infrastructure, and an under-developed talent pool. It's worth noting that historical colonialism came to an end through legal change, leaving intact the coloniality that underpins it, and allowing for coloniality to continue fostering new forms of colonial dynamics such as the one here being called data colonialism(Couldry & Mejias, 2019; Mumford, 2021).

This message is not targeting any individuals in high or low places. It is addressing itself addressing ourselves to the analogues of territorial and structural coloniality that endure in the digital age. It is identifying metropolises—the centers of power—and their often oppressed peripheries. It is contesting the metropole's authority sway and influence in shaping everyday life(Champion, 2005). The emerging theories of data colonialism(Mumford, 2021) and platform governance(Gorwa, 2019) recognize this nature of historic continuity and the desire of Western tech monopolies to dominate, control and influence social, political, and cultural discourse. This uneven distribution is enacted through extractive and exploitative behaviour and justified by the association of networked technologies with the political and social benefits of online community, drawing upon narratives that generally fall within the rubric of technological utopianism. We thus have to reform and restructure the entire system. Setting up this new system may well be a job for young people who can envision novel possibilities for a better African future. The old political joke which circulated in East Germany in the late 1980's – that the last one to leave the country should switch off the lights – does not work in Africa. It is time for conscientious citizens and all who love this continent to stand up for something that seems impossible to achieve by conventional reason or rational reckoning: a totally new system and social contract which steers a productive and upright course for an uncorrupted future.

A moment to reflect: Three Scenarios

While acknowledging the damaging potentials of digital colonialism when actions of good men and good women are Africa's highest needs, we will now take a very brief look at the digital futures in terms of three possible outcomes, a worst case scenario, a least worst case scenario, and a utopian best case scenario. With regard to the worst case scenario the cautionary aspects in need of attention are, first, the past of this continent and, second, the fact that it can only become worse.

The worst case scenario for Africa from today's perspective would be a digital war,

whether internal or external. If the 20th century engineers of consent had magnifying glasses and baseball bats as their weapons, those of the 21st century have acquired telescopes, microscopes and scalpels in the shape of algorithms and analytics as their new weapon of war (Tufekci, 2014). But how should we approach these algorithms in the first place? Should we treat them as lines of code, weapons, as objects or should we see them as social processes in which the social world is embodied in the substrate of the code? Exploring the notion of algorithms enables us to see how algorithms also play a part in social ordering processes, both in terms of how the algorithm is used to promote certain visions of calculative objectivity and also in relation to the wider governmentalities that this concept might be used to open up (Beer, 2017). It is important to consider who is included in this new configuration, who is not, and how this is like or unlike previous instantiations. The factors contributing to the war risk for this continent are unfortunately several, spanning from fears of historically aggressive state actors to the intransigence of belligerent neighbors and the arrogance of pressure mongering distant powers. In our view, this creates a contradiction between the demand for established wisdom – whereby needed intervention involves technical expertise and years of professional experience – and an impossibility of relying on the presently known exponents of expertise and experience.

If the experience of the brute force domination used by colonialist in this continent is any indicator, a digital war would be devastating for the people and livelihoods overall and it would also widen to the extreme gap between Africa and the so-called Global North for reason of which Africa is already trailing behind peer economies which possess highly trained human capital and cultural resources. But even more perversely, the war economy would have a few large scale winners and even more small profiteers who would not pursue peace as long as they benefit from the digital war. The continent would likely descend into total inequality, impoverishment of the many, and lasting external dependency.

The second scenario would be the least worst. Like the worst-case scenario this least worst case model could be by the superficial observer be easily confused with the continent's existence before the worst case but its inner characteristics would differ greatly. The scenario might furthermore be evolving somewhat unpredictably i.e. conceivably with some productively synergies of development realized by virtue of international influences. As per the conditionality's of currently offered international funds inflows on the implementation of reforms and more reforms to achieve digital connectivity – iterated since decades but externally enforced through digital colonialism, this scenario necessarily begins with reforms adopted and implemented by the vision-oriented Africans – meaning the total cleanup – now generation of new and untested representatives and aspiring leaders. Handled by international expert advisors – with their own interest – they would create the digital

governance administrative core a continent whose willing allegiance to foreign interest is cemented for decades. The digital economy could be streamlined to comply with either the interest of the surveillance capitalists West or the data controlled state capitalist East.

Instead of being constantly disrupted by fragmented and contradictory local interest as a result of its extremely diverse political, social and economic situation, Africa tech ecosystem could be managed under coordinated interest of geopolitical bloc that it becomes integrated in. The tradeoff, however, would dictate that it would lose its uniqueness of its own vision and gain the surety of dependence. This surety will fundamentally have to entail dependence on the geopolitical bloc's dominant values but allow for collateral benefits owing to 21st century economic elements of interdependence and mutual prosperity. Also on the historical balance sheet, Africa will lose all of its fake rentier economic gains in digital governance and see its overall societal wealth greatly reduced but, going forward, could maintain and even develop a part of its economic and technology specificity.

Lastly, the utopian scenario. Based on the assumption of a development and innovative capability of Africans even in a situation of a lack of intellectual property and data governance frameworks, a utopian scenario is justified in our view. This aspirational assertion has to be qualified by the notion that such a scenario of prosperity, while ambitious by design, would be sheer madness if presented as a comprehensive plan or coherent roadmap. Any utopian scenario is only legitimate as a suggestive and hopeful vision. Such a vision, however, may trigger the realization of micro-realities that can influence the worst case scenario referenced above. Without trying to detail any of them, Africa from 2020-yes, has an abundant potential to innovate and test economic and social solutions that can help make the future of its people more sustainable and livable. There is a need for solutions to achieve our shared commitments to achieve each and every one of the Sustainable Development Goals (SGDs), a set of 17 socio-economic, political and environmental objectives forming and structuring the development agenda of the next 8 years(Amoore, 2013). There is need for solutions in effective digital government and digital infrastructures of the private sector economy. This reservoir of issues is just to name but the first line of items where every current need and unfulfilled want represents opportunities for multi-level digital entrepreneurial actions, in form of policy improvement, digital economy integration, micro-economic innovation, and business innovation.

In the big picture, the potentials for African creativity in the digital future are real but have two preconditions. First, that economic and digital opportunities are equitable, socially licensed and universally accepted and that opportunity taking has to be qualified by the expectation and willingness to satisfy the societal need for

better sharing of economic and social burdens. Second, the platform needed for such future flourishing is implemented designed and inclusively and democratically. As to these second precondition for digital inclusivity and democracy, there are no real precedents for systemic reinvention but there are rich examples of both very beneficial and less successful practical transitions into new systems of inclusivity and democracy in the late 17th, 18th, and especially the 20th century beginning at the end of World War II. In Africa, the path will in our view start with a systemic sweep that cleans out the historical legacies of coloniality that remain unquestioned in the digital present.

We call upon Africa's internal and external observers of good will to view the entire digital economy as an entrepreneurship project. Let us just bet that with this transformation of attitudes the spirit of entrepreneurship can create Africa's next *annus mirabilis*. To make headway in the global digital economy, Africans will need gold standard resources, talent and connectivity. Digital globalization, a natural requirement and outcome of scientific and technological progress, is the irreversible trend of the scientific times ahead.

Africa's Tech Ecosystem

Africans are innovative; we just tend to keep quiet about our innovation. Consider Nigeria's Kudi.ai which allows users to improve the process of money transfers through natural languages and AI(Kudi.ai., n.d.); AI Expo Africa, a business focused AI and Data Science Community in Africa(AI Expo Africa., n.d.); Stellenbosch and Makerere University Masters in AI and Data Science launched in 2020(University, 2020) and 2021(Makerere University, 2021) in partnership with DeepMind to provide state of the art research exposure and teaching by experts to African students; Deep Learning Indaba, an organization with a mission of strengthening African capacity in machine learning and recognizing excellence in research and innovation across the continent(Indaba, 2019). All these initiatives are spurring active interest in Africa's AI ecosystem and creating a community of young people interested in AI(UNESCO, 2019)while at the same time fostering an ecosystem where mentorship is available to guide young people.

The new digital ecosystem being propelled by a handful of tech titans, primarily the so-called FAANGs - Facebook, Apple, Amazon, Netflix and Google, in the west, and a comparable group in China - Alibaba, Tencent, Baidu, and Xiaomi, are neither saint nor sinner in this disruptive world where technology is transforming competitiveness and markets. They cannot be a blocker to new digital firms springing up and serving global markets from Africa. Take an example of Kenya's Zindi, a data science competition platform that hosts an ecosystem of scientists, engineers, academics, companies, NGOs, governments and institutions – all focused on solving Africa's most pressing problems by developing, curating, and preparing

data-driven challenges (Zindi, n.d.) to Madagascar's, SmartOne, a data annotation service that provides high quality and high scale human-in-the-loop data to feed AI and ML projects(SmartOne., 2020), Africa's future competitiveness depends on entrepreneurs, expanding digital infrastructure, and enhancing digital skills. The covid-19 pandemic has also given a spotlight to African youth innovative spirit. Of the thousand new or modifications of existing technologies that have been developed worldwide to target different areas of the COVID-19 response, World Health Organization (WHO) analysis reveals that Africa accounts for 12.8 per cent of the innovations, ranging from surveillance, contact tracing, community engagement, treatment, laboratory systems and infection prevention and control(WHO Regional Office for Africa, 2020). Some examples that have emerged across the continent include: Wiqaytna, developed in Morocco, which notifies people who have been in contact with a person who tested positive for COVID-19; and Global Mama, from Ghana, which produces reusable masks and designs automated, contact-free and solar-powered washing stations using locally sourced materials(*Economic and Social Council Youth Forum 10 th Anniversary: Supporting the Culture of Innovation , Creativity and Entrepreneurship of African Youth to Build Forward Better for Sustainable Development*, 2021).

Beyond disruption: Leveraging openness to meet challenges of our time

Developing open science approaches will therefore be a critical enabler in accelerating innovations and thankfully many initiatives on the continent facilitate and support these commons. Open approaches are supportive of developmental efforts because they enable collaboration that can generate more efficient and more robust solutions to whatever challenge confronts society, institutions or persons. UNESCO has compiled a list of open access initiatives across the continent(UNESCO, n.d.). One example is the African Open Science Platform (AOSP) animated by a vision for African scientists to be at the cutting edge of contemporary, data-intensive science as a fundamental resource for a modern society; to be innovative global exponents and advocates of Open Science; and to be leaders in addressing African and Global Challenges(AU Department of Human Resources., 2019). At its 3rd ordinary session, the African Union Specialized Technical Committee on Education, Science and Technology (AU STC-EST) declared that they support and promote open science initiatives at the national, regional and continental levels to increase access to scientific information, data, knowledge and networks and to bring science closer to society(African Union, 2019).Globally, UNESCO also initiated a consultative process that led to the adoption of a recommendation on open science in November 2021, and which will be a standard setting instrument following the decision at the General Conference during its 41st Session(P Oti-boateng, 2020; UNESCO, 2021b). Even during the pandemic open Science practices have gained traction. One example is an open letter that was

signed by more than 140 world leaders ahead of the health ministers' World Health Assembly meeting held on 18 May 2020 calling for an open people's vaccine for COVID-19(UNAIDS, 2020). Several projects utilizing open-source approaches commenced soon after the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic. A white paper authored in August 2020 by the The AU High Level Panel on Emerging Technologies (APET) cited an ongoing work by a team at the University of Cape Town's development of Covi-ID32, a contact tracing open source platform for African contexts which have limited smartphone penetration(AUDA-NEPAD, 2020). The fact that the platform is open source promotes individual exploration, particularly in a research or business context. For instance, the development and widespread use of artificial intelligence and machine learning has been facilitated by availability of open source datasets in GitHub(GitHub, n.d.) with no paper work needed to access them in order to train machine algorithms at the data input level(Davis, 2019). Without these open source projects, AI as we know it could not exist.

AU STI instruments, institutions and initiatives

Regionally, there are also Science Technology and Innovation (STI) instruments, institutions and initiatives driving the AI sector in Africa, namely Common Market for Eastern and Southern Africa (COMESA), East African Community (EAC), Economic Community of Central African States (ECCAS), Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS), Intergovernmental Authority on Development (IGAD), Community of Sahel-Saharan States (CEN-SAD), Southern African Development Community (SADC) and Arab Maghreb Union (AMU). Amongst these, COMESA, EAC, ECOWAS and SADC have the well-developed STI co-operation instruments and institutions. The others only have foundational provisions in their constitutive treaties, but they have not developed supplementary STI instruments and their requisite implementing structures(AU (2014) *Supra* at 49–50; ARIA VII *Supra* 91–92, *Citing Arts 7 and 13A of the Agreement Establishing IGAD.*, n.d.).

COMESA established its Innovation Council in 2012(Awards, 2012) and launched it in 2013. The terms of reference of the Innovation Council, convened by COMESA Secretary general, include advising the COMESA committee on STI, members states and regional centers of excellence; participating in the drafting of the COMESA Innovation Roadmap and advising on its implementation; promoting STI collaboration with international and regional institutions; overseeing the design and launch of an annual innovation forum and overseeing the design and launch of the COMESA Innovation Award.

EAC's Science and Technology Commission's (EASTECO) main objective is to 'promote and coordinate the development, management and application of Science and Technology in the Partner States'.(Art 5 *Protocol on the Establishment of the East African Science and Technology Commission (EASTECO)*, n.d.) The

Protocol lists seven specific items flowing from this broad objective, which include: promoting cooperation in the development of regional science and technology policies; facilitating the joint development and application of Science and Technology for the Community; and enabling cooperation in the joint research and development in science and technology'. The EAC's Inter-University Council for East Africa has also been identified as a significant role player in the regional STI landscape. It has a broad mandate relating to the co-operation between institutions of higher learning in the EAC and advises partner states(*The Inter-University Council for East Africa Act, 2009 (as Amended in 2012)*, n.d.).

ECOWAS' STI co-operation has several STI related instruments, namely the Protocol on Education and Training(*ECOWAS Protocol A/P3/1/03 on Education and Training*, n.d.); the ECOWAS Policy on STI (ECOPOST) and its Plan of Action;(*ECOWAS Supplementary Act A/SA.2/06/12 Adopting the ECOWAS Policy on Science, Technology and Innovation and Its Plan of Action.*, n.d.) and the Directive on STI(*ECOWAS Directive A/DIR.1/06/12 on STI.*, n.d.). The directive states that the broad objective of the ECOWAS STI cooperation is to 'achieve sustainable economic and social development through the implementation of a policy of "Science, Technology and Innovation" to meet the current and future needs of the peoples and guarantee them a better quality of life'. It then details specific objectives which include developing the STI institutional framework, policy and plan of action in each member state, attending to the 'financial capacities of scientific and technological research institutions', 'strengthening human and technical capacities in science and technology, and promoting technological development and transfer'

SADC has formulated and adopted SADC Vision 2050 and the RISDP 2020–2030, which similarly prioritise STI in alignment with Agenda 2063(Southern Africa Today, 2020). The preamble to the SADC Protocol on STI, 2008, notes that it is premised on 'the critical importance given to STI' by the Regional Indicative Strategic Development Plan (RISDP) and notes 'the importance of IPR protection in promoting the development and application of STI'. The broad objective of the protocol 'is to foster cooperation and promote the development, transfer and mastery of STI in Member States' to meet detailed specific objectives(*Art 2 SADC Protocol on STI.*, n.d.). These specific objectives include strategic planning, gender(*Art 2(p) SADC Protocol on STI.*, n.d.), indigenous knowledge systems (IKS)(*Art 2(h) SADC Protocol on STI.*, n.d.), and IPRs(*Art 2(m) SADC Protocol on STI.*, n.d.). It entered into force in 2017.

Despite concerted efforts to harness STI for development through Science, Technology and Innovation Strategy for Africa (STISA-2024) and related strategies several challenges to the use of STI policies to provide an enabling environment for innovation still persist. Implementation capacity is constrained by inadequate

critical technical skills and resources to promote R&D, improve higher education, and foster growth(UNESCO, 2021a). This, coupled with reliance on external funding and dependence on imported raw materials, means that most African economies lack the diversity and resilience needed to generate internal funding and investment in capacity enhancement.

Conclusion

What does the future hold in store? It is essential for Africans not to become merely observers of ongoing AI advances but be active shapers, producers and users of these technologies. The research and innovation journey to connect these new technology with our all familiar every day and working lives has only just begun. We should be very attentive to the direction it will take us in the coming years. Longer-term initiatives to support equitable entrepreneurship in the digital age are still needed. Digital development is driven by revolutionary interdisciplinary and collaborative innovation in science and technology and industries; and impeded by unilateralism. There are decades where nothing happens and there are weeks where decades can happen. This saying is particularly apt to describe what has transpired during the pandemic, and will continue to be tested. Visions of enhancing science, technology and innovation driven through the STI Strategy for Africa (STISA-2024) in the African Union Agenda 2063 framework(African Union Commission, 2015), a 50-year plan 'for inclusive growth and sustainable development for Africa' adopted in 2013, needs to be pulled forward to 2030 by our pandemic realities. Previous connectivity recommendations that used a five to 10 year horizon for implementation need to shift to a one to 5 year horizon or sooner. During the Trump administrative H1-B Visa ban (WSJ, 2019), we had a window to attract and retain the brightest mind in Africa. It is time for Africa to broaden its tech approach to include policy framework such as competition and regulatory policy, and intellectual property regimes and how they encourage or impede innovative firms.

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